

Food and Agriculture
Organization of the
United Nations

The International Treaty

ON PLANT GENETIC RESOURCES
FOR FOOD AND AGRICULTURE

XML integration protocol of the Global Information System

History of changes

This document is available at

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Please refer to the above URL for the latest version of this document.

Version	Date	Description
4.1	24/05/2024	Removed element <source> for <i>in situ</i> material. Minor fixes. Deposited on Zenodo
4.0	31/07/2022	Updated for <i>in situ</i> material. Dropped reference to transfer transactions
3.9	31/07/2023	Updated with the new GLIS URL
3.8	15/10/2019	Clarified that the PID of the holder is mandatory because it is always available. Updated label of Method code "obin" to Inherited to harmonize it with the latest version of the Descriptors
3.7	07/05/2019	Increased max length of georeferencing method. Edited the wording on MLS status in Table 5 to match the Descriptors document
3.6	10/11/2018	Added n/a (Other) to identifier types (Table 4). Added new user-defined codes to ISO-3166 alpha-3 to designate CGIAR centers
3.5	09/02/2018	Clarified description of <historical>. Added endpoint <code>addtargets</code> to add new targets to existing DOIs. Clarified that Easy-SMTA PIDs should always be provided when available, even if the WIEWS code is already provided. Modified behavior of <code>update</code> regarding targets. If no target is specified in the <code>update</code> message, targets and associated keyword codes are left unchanged. Harmonized with version 2.1 of document "Data required for the assignation of Digital Object Identifiers in the Global Information System"
3.4	21/07/2017	Modified element <exist> into <historical>
3.3	20/07/2017	Updated to new version of descriptors. Species (specific epithet) is now a mandatory descriptor but, if not provided, <i>sp.</i> is assumed. Physical existence of the material is no longer assumed. The new element <exist> is introduced with values <i>y</i> or <i>n</i> . If empty or not present, <i>y</i> is assumed. New target keyword list
3.2	16/07/2017	Restructured registration and update XML to support XSD validation.
3.1	12/07/2017	Removed identifier type GenesysID and fixed case in registration example. Improved explanation of <error> element.
3.0	25/06/2017	Added transfer transaction
2.0	17/05/2017	Added update transaction
1.2	19/04/2017	Added HTTP response code 503 due to maintenance.
1.1	11/04/2017	Better described the format of error messages that may be returned before the XML is parsed. Added <genus> to the HTTPS reply to address those cases in which <sampleid> alone would not be sufficient to uniquely identify the record to update.
1.0	29/03/2017	Removed geographic coordinates from holding location. Updated link to Descriptors document
0.16	28/03/2017	Changed document name to "XML integration protocol". Changed test URL
0.15	22/03/2017	Corrected element <progdoi> to have one or more children <doi>
0.14	21/02/2017	Removed <historical> element because registration assumes that the material is available
0.13	06/02/2017	Changed format of DMS coordinates to ddDmmMssSX
0.12	02/02/2017	Updated to match v2 of the descriptors
0.11	31/01/2017	Corrected code for "Other" in Table 4 "biostatus" to make it directly compatible with MCPD

0.10	02/12/2016	Clarified that address is optional in actor and location elements. Added historical and user-defined country codes. Added minimal example
0.9	14/11/2016	idType codes are now all lowercase
0.8	03/11/2016	Described the registration process in natural language
0.7	02/11/2016	Clarified that each XML registration request must contain a single <register> element with a single PGRFA inside
0.6	01/11/2016	Added PURL to idType and pictures to target keywords
0.5	25/10/2016	Added missing table on bioStatus codes. Corrected idType codes. Added new target keywords
0.4	24/10/2016	Removed language code from crop name element
0.3	14/09/2016	Separate species, species authority, subtaxa and subtaxon authority for better MCPD and DarwinCore compatibility
0.2	02/05/2016	Added possibility of providing an existing DOI for the material being registered
0.1	30/03/2016	Initial draft

Introduction

This document describes the XML object to register Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture (PGRFA) to the Global Information System (GLIS) of the International Treaty on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture (ITPGRFA). Upon successful registration, GLIS will return the Digital Object Identifier (DOI) associated with PGRFA.

GLIS also allow for the update of descriptors associated to a PGRFA already registered.

For confidentiality, all transactions are performed using HTTPS, the secure version of the HTTP protocol. To establish a secure HTTP connection to the **test server**, the external system must send the request to the following URL (port 443):

for *ex situ* material

<https://glis.qa.fao.org/glis/xml/manager?constype=ex>

for *in situ* material

<https://glis.qa.fao.org/glis/xml/manager?constype=in>

and properly handle the HTTPS handshake. **For backward compatibility, should constype not be present in the URL above, it will be assumed to be ex.** It is recommended to check the documentation corresponding to the development language used on the external system's side to properly format the XML object.

The above URL is the unique entry point for all transactions described in this document: registration and update, both for *ex situ* and *in situ* material.

The UTF-8 character set is required to be specified in the `encoding` attribute of the XML object.

Please note that the above URLs are for testing only. The credentials to be provided in the HTTPS request must be requested to the ITPGRFA Secretariat via an email to PGRFA-Treaty@fao.org. The URL of the production server's unique entry point as well as the final access credentials will be provided once the tests are successfully completed.

For additional details on the meaning of each element please refer to the latest version of document "Digital Object Identifiers for food crops" available at

<http://www.fao.org/3/l8840EN/i8840en.pdf>

The above document refers to *ex situ* material; at the time of this writing, the corresponding document for *in situ* material is still being finalized.

While only a handful of descriptors are mandatory for registration, it is strongly recommended to provide as much information as possible to allow GLIS to offer more powerful services to its users.

The registration process can be described in natural language as follows:

```
Query your database to find all records that need to be registered
For each of the records found above repeat {
  Compile the XML registration document as described below
  Encapsulate the XML registration document into a HTTPS POST request
  Send the HTTPS POST request to the GLIS URL
```

```

Examine the XML response message received by GLIS
If the response contains an <error> element {
    Log the XML response somewhere for further inspection
} else {
    update local database using something like:
    UPDATE {yourTable}
        SET doi = {<doi> element of the response}
        WHERE {your sampleid column} = {<sampleid> element of the response};
}
}

```

In some institutions, `sampleid` alone is not unique because numbering is done separately for different collections; to deal with these cases, GLIS returns the genus of the PGRFA if provided in the registration request. Therefore, the UPDATE SQL statement above would be

```

UPDATE {yourTable}
    SET doi = {<doi> element of the response}
    WHERE
        {your sampleid column} = {<sampleid> element of the response}
        AND
        {your genus column} = {<genus> element of the response};

```

For *in situ* material, instead of the sample ID, the population ID will be used. Some requests may fail for a variety of reasons (see “Error conditions” below). You should inspect the errors logged, adopt the necessary correcting measures and submit the failed requests again. GLIS provides error messages that are usually self-explanatory. In case of need, please do not hesitate to contact us for assistance.

The update transaction works in a very similar fashion to the registration transaction.

HTTPS request

The external system must send requests to GLIS using an HTTPS POST request with the XML document described below as request body. The XML document is not compressed.

As per XML standard, newlines can be inserted into the element value either through the `` escape sequence or explicitly. For instance, the following two elements are equivalent:

```
<xxx>This is the first line&#xD;This is the second line</xxx>
```

```
<xxx>This is the first line
This is the second line</xxx>
```

System unavailability

GLIS may be unavailable due to scheduled maintenance activities. In this case, sending a request will result in a HTTP response code 503: *Service Unavailable* and there will be no response body. It is therefore necessary to check the HTTP code of the response before attempting to process the response.

Error conditions

Upon receiving the HTTPS request, GLIS performs some preliminary checks that may result in an error response with the following structure:

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<response>
  <error>[message]</error>
</response>
```

where `[message]` can be one of the following:

Access denied

The username and or password specified in the XML document are not valid. Contact the GLIS System Administrator at PGRFA-Treaty@fao.org to obtain valid access credentials. Please note that username and password to be used in the XML document are not the same used to login to GLIS as user.

Request sent over HTTP instead of HTTPS

For security reasons, GLIS requires HTTPS. Please adjust your sending application to use HTTPS.

XML parsing errors

When the XML document is parsed by GLIS, some errors may be found as detailed in the error message. Please note that any error listed here refers to the XML syntax and not to the content of the XML document, which will be analyzed next.

If none of the above error conditions occurs, GLIS validates the XML object included in the HTTPS POST and responds with an XML object depending on the success or failure and the type of the transaction as described in the corresponding chapter.

Content errors

After the HTTPS method is verified, the syntax of the XML document has been validated and the login credentials accepted, the XML document is checked for content errors. For instance, incorrect ISO-3 country codes or non-existing codes. If any content error is found, a self-explanatory message will be appended to the `<error>` element.

PGRFA registration (for *ex situ* material)

While they have a very similar structure, the registration and update messages differ for *ex situ* and *in situ* materials. In this chapter, the registration message for *ex situ* material is described, please refer to the corresponding chapter for the *in situ* material.

The purpose of this transaction is to obtain a DOI associated to the PGRFA by providing a set of descriptors in the registration request. However, if a DOI obtained through a service other than GLIS is already associated to the PGRFA, such DOI must be provided in the request so that GLIS will not assign a new DOI but adopt the one provided.

The registration message contains metadata to be associated to the DOI. Providing as much information as possible is recommended because it will facilitate users when they resolve DOIs in GLIS or discover PGRFA using the metadata provided.

Request

The general structure of the XML registration request is as follows:

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="utf-8"?>
<register>
  <mandatory elements>
    <highly recommended elements>
      <context elements>
    </register>
```

There is only one `<register>` element referring to a single PGRFA. It contains mandatory elements and may contain optional and context elements. Context elements are in turn grouped into elements (`<acquisition>`, `<collection>` and `<breeding>`); one or more elements can be specified depending on the information being provided.

Minimal example

The following is a minimal example with just mandatory and some highly recommended elements.

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<register username="cgn" password="Passw0rd">
  <location>
    <pid>00AC55</pid>
  </location>
  <sampleid>CGN00001</sampleid>
  <date>1986-05-12</date>
  <method>acqu</method>
  <genus>Hordeum</genus>
  <cropnames>
    <name>Barley</name>
  </cropnames>
```

```

<targets>
  <target>
    <value>http://www.nordgen.org/sgsv/index.php?unit_id=239741</value>
    <kws>
      <kw>5</kw>
    </kws>
  </target>
</targets>
<biostatus>300</biostatus>
<species>vulgare</species>
<spauth>L.</spauth>
<subtaxa>subsp. vulgare</subtaxa>
<stauth>L.</stauth>
<names>
  <name>Maartsche Gerst</name>
</names>
<ids>
  <id type="sgsvid">239741</id>
  <id type="genesysuid">urn:uuid:89e8a52d-5b79-4510-b209-af0f48254cea</id>
</ids>
<mlsstatus>1</mlsstatus>
<historical>n</historical>
<acquisition>
  <provider>
    <wiews>NLD078</wiews>
  </provider>
  <sampleid>GZ A1</sampleid>
  <provenance>NLD</provenance>
</acquisition>
</register>

```

Actor or location element

In some cases, a block of elements is used to identify an actor or the location where the PGRFA is conserved. Actors are:

- provider of the PGRFA
- collector(s)
- breeder(s)

In all these cases, the composition of the elements block is the same:

```

<wiews>[wiews]</wiews>
<pid>[pid]</pid>
<name>[name]</name>
<address>[address]</address>
<country>[country]</country>

```

Where:

- [wiews] is the FAO WIEWS Institute code (<http://www.fao.org/wiews>)
- [pid] is the Permanent Identifier assigned by Easy-SMTA (<https://mls.planttreaty.org>)
- [name] is the name of the individual or organization
- [address] is the address of the individual or organization
- [country] is the ISO-3166 alpha-3 country code (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ISO_3166-1_alpha-3) with the extensions listed in Table 7

For registration, the <pid> is always available (because DOI registrants must be registered users of Easy-SMTA) and must be used in the location where the PGRFA is conserved (if available, the WIEWS code should also be provided). For other actors, providing the WIEWS code or the PID is enough. GLIS can fetch the information from WIEWS or Easy-SMTA as appropriate. However, for provider, collectors

and breeders, when neither the WIEWS institute code nor the Easy-SMTA PID is available, the other three elements should be indicated. For instance, in the case of <breeder>, the following alternatives are equivalent:

WIEWS Institute code	Easy-SMTA PID	Neither of the two
<pre><breeder> <wiews>PHL001</wiews> </breeder></pre>	<pre><breeder> <pid>00AB40</pid> </breeder></pre>	<pre><breeder> <name>IRRI</name> <address>Los Baños, Laguna</address> <country>PHL</country> </breeder></pre>

If more than one among <wiews>, <pid> and the explicit elements (<name>, <address> and <country>) are present, the order of precedence is <pid> => <wiews> => explicit elements. If explicit elements are used, at least name and country must be present, address is optional.

XML request object

The body of the HTTPS POST registration request is as follows. Elements marked with * can be repeated. Some elements can be specified instead of others. See the element description for mandatory requirements and other details. The order of the elements within their parent element is irrelevant. Optional elements may be indicated as empty (e.g. <element/> or <element></element>) or omitted altogether.

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<register username="[username]" password="[password]">
  <location> <!-- Location element -->
    <wiews>[lwiews]</wiews>
    <pid>[lpid]</pid>
    <name>[lname]</name>
    <address>[laddress]</address>
    <country>[lcountry]</country>
  </location>
  <sampledoi>[sampledoi]</sampledoi>
  <sampleid>[sampleid]</sampleid>
  <date>[date]</date>
  <method>[method]</method>
  <genus>[genus]</genus>
  <cropnames>
    <name>[cropname]</name>*
  </cropnames>
  <targets>
    <target>*
      <value>[tvalue]</value>
      <kws>
        <kw>[tkw]</kw>*
      </kws>
    </target>
  </targets>
  <progdoi>
    <doi>[progdoi]</doi>*
  </progdoi>
  <biostatus>[biostatus]</biostatus>
  <species>[species]</species>
  <spauth>[spauth]</spauth>
  <subtaxa>[subtaxa]</subtaxa>
  <stauth>[stauth]</stauth>
  <names>
    <name>[nvalue]</name>*
  </names>
  <ids>
    <id type="[itype]">[ivalue]</id>*
  </ids>
  <mlsstatus>[mlsstatus]</mlsstatus>
  <historical>[hist]</historical>
  <acquisition>
    <provider> <!-- Actor element -->
    <wiews>[pwiews]</wiews>
```

```

    <pid>[ppid]</pid>
    <name>[pname]</name>
    <address>[paddress]</address>
    <country>[pcountry]</country>
  </provider>
  <sampleid>[psampleid]</sampleid>
  <provenance>[provenance]</provenance>
</acquisition>
<collection>
  <collectors>
    <collector>*      <!-- Actor element -->
      <wiews>[cwiews]</wiews>
      <pid>[cpid]</pid>
      <name>[cname]</name>
      <address>[caddress]</address>
      <country>[ccountry]</country>
    </collector>
  </collectors>
  <sampleid>[csampleid]</sampleid>
  <missid>[missid]</missid>
  <site>[site]</site>
  <lat>[clat]</lat>
  <lon>[clon]</lon>
  <uncert>[uncert]</uncert>
  <datum>[datum]</datum>
  <georef>[georef]</georef>
  <elevation>[elevation]</elevation>
  <date>[cdate]</date>
  <source>[source]</source>
</collection>
<breeding>
  <breeders>
    <breeder>* <!-- Actor element -->
      <wiews>[wiews]</wiews>
      <pid>[pid]</pid>
      <name>[name]</name>
      <address>[address]</address>
      <country>[country]</country>
    </breeder>
  </breeders>
  <ancestry>[ancestry]</ancestry>
</breeding>
</register>

```

where (unless otherwise specified, elements are optional, the DID column refers to the descriptor ID in the document " Digital Object Identifiers for food crops " mentioned above:

Field	DID	Type	Max length or format	Description
[username]	N/A	String	128	Username assigned by the GLIS System Administrator to the requesting system. Mandatory.
[password]	N/A	String	128	Password assigned by the GLIS System Administrator to the requesting system. Mandatory.
[lwiews]	M01	String	16	FAO WIEWS Institute code of the organization where the PGRFA is conserved. See "Actor or location element" for details.
[lpid]	M01	String	16	Easy-SMTA PID of the organization, legal entity or individual conserving the PGRFA. Mandatory. See "Actor or location element" for details.
[lname]	M01	String	128	Surname and name of individuals or organization name of the organization or legal entity conserving the PGRFA. See "Actor or location element" for details.
[laddress]	M01	String	128	Address of the organization, legal entity or individual conserving the PGRFA. See "Actor or location element" for details.
[lcountry]	M01	String	3	ISO-3166 alpha-3 country code (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ISO_3166-1_alpha-3) of the

				organization, legal entity or individual conserving the PGRFA. See "Actor or location element" and Table 7 for details.
[sampledoi]	N/A	String	128	A Digital Object Identifier (DOI) obtained from a service other than GLIS and that is already assigned to the PGRFA.
[sampleid]	M02	String	128	A string that <i>uniquely</i> identifies the PGRFA that is being registered in holder's collection. This value will be returned by GLIS in the response message and is assumed to be used to associate the DOI to the corresponding material in the local database. You must provide <sampleid> even if <sampledoi> is provided. In case you use the DOI as unique identifier in your local database, you can repeat it in <sampleid>. Mandatory. Please read more details in the "HTTPS reply" chapter.
[date]	M03	Date	YYYY-MM-DD	Date in which PGRFA became part of the collection. Date fragments (YYYY-MM and YYYY) are also accepted.
[method]	M04	String	4	Method through which the PGRFA has been obtained. Mandatory. See Table 1 for the codes accepted by this element.
[genus]	M05	String	64	The taxon of the genus for the PGRFA. At least one between <genus> and <cropname> must be provided.
[species]	M05	String	128	Specific epithet of the PGRFA scientific name. If not provided, sp. is assumed
[cropname]	M05	String	128	Common name of the PGRFA or crop name. At least one between <genus> and <cropname> must be provided. Multiple <name> elements are allowed.
[tvalue]	R01	String	256	URL of the web page where additional information on the PGRFA can be found. The URL must be URL-encoded. Any number of <target> elements can be provided.
[tkw]	R01	String	16	Code of the keyword indicating the type of information that will be found at the given target URL. See Table 2 below.
[progdoi]	R02	String	GLIS DOI	DOI of the PGRFA(s) from which the current PGRFA was derived. The DOI must be registered in GLIS. Please note that the number of allowed DOIs depends on the method as follows: Acquisition: 1 DOI In-house copy: 1 DOI In-house variant: 1 DOI Novel distinct PGRFA: 1 or more DOIs Observation - Natural: 0 DOI Inherited: 0 DOI
[biostatus]	R03	String	3	Biological status of the PGRFA. See Table 3 below.
[spauth]	R04	String	64	Authority for the specific epithet
[subtaxa]	R04	String	128	Any additional infra-specific taxon such as subspecies, variety, form, group and so on
[stauth]	R04	String	64	Authority for the subtaxon at the most detailed level provided
[nvalue]	R05	String	128	Other name or designations of the PGRFA. Any number of <name> elements can be provided.
[itype]	R06	String	16	Code of the identifier type. The attribute is mandatory. See Table 4 below.
[ivalue]	R06	String	128	Other identifier of the type indicated by the attribute <i>type</i> assigned to the PGRFA
[mlsstatus]	R07	String	2	Code that identifies the status of the PGRFA with regard to the MLS. See Table 5 below.
[hist]	R08	String	1	Indicates whether the PGRFA no longer exists. Allowed value is y/n with y=material is no longer available and n=material available
[pwiews]	A01	String	16	FAO WIEWS code of the organization providing the PGRFA. See "Actor element" for details.
[ppid]	A01	String	16	Easy-SMTA PID of the organization, legal entity or individual providing the PGRFA. See "Actor element" for details.
[pname]	A01	String	128	Surname and name for individuals or organization or legal entity name of the provider. See "Actor element" for details.

[paddress]	A01	String	128	Address of the organization, legal entity or individual providing the PGRFA. multiple lines are accepted. See "Actor element" for details.
[pcountry]	A01	String	3	ISO-3166 alpha-3 country code (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ISO_3166-1_alpha-3) of the organization, legal entity or individual providing the PGRFA. See "Actor element" and Table 7 for details.
[psampleid]	A02	String	128	Unique identifier for the PGRFA in the provider's management.
[provenance]	A03	String	3	ISO-3166 alpha-3 country code (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ISO_3166-1_alpha-3) of the country in which the PGRFA material was either collected or bred or selected, or the first country in the known history of the PGRFA. See Table 7 for details
[cwiews]	A04	String	16	FAO WIEWS code of the organization collecting the PGRFA. See "Actor element" for details. Any number of <collector> can be provided.
[cpid]	A04	String	16	Easy-SMTA PID of the organization, legal entity or individual collecting the PGRFA. See "Actor element" for details.
[cname]	A04	String	128	Surname and name for individuals or organization or legal entity name of the collector. See "Actor element" and Table 7 for details.
[caddress]	A04	String	128	Address of the organization, legal entity or individual collecting the PGRFA. Multiple lines are accepted. See "Actor element" and Table 7 for details.
[ccountry]	A04	String	3	ISO-3166 alpha-3 country code (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ISO_3166-1_alpha-3) of the country of the organization, legal entity or individual collecting the PGRFA. See "Actor element" and Table 7 for details.
[csampleid]	A05	String	128	Identifier assigned by the collector(s) to the PGRFA collected.
[missid]	A06	String	128	Identifier of the collecting mission
[site]	A07	String	128	Description of the location where the PGRFA was collected
[clat]	A08	String	10	Latitude where the PGRFA was collected in either ddd.xxxxx (up to 5 decimals, preceded by minus sign for S) format or dd°mm'ss"X (where X is N or S). No spaces are allowed.
[clon]	A09	String	10	Longitude where the PGRFA was collected in either ddd.xxxxx (up to 5 decimals, preceded by minus sign for W) format or dd°mm'ss"X (where X is E or W). No spaces are allowed.
[uncert]	A10	Integer		Uncertainty of lat/lon coordinates in metres
[datum]	A11	String	16	Geodetic <i>datum</i> of the lat/lon coordinates
[georef]	A12	String	128	Georeferencing method, e.g. GPS
[elevation]	A13	Integer		Elevation of collecting site in metres above sea level
[cdate]	A14	Date	YYYY-MM-DD	Date on which the PGRFA was collected. Date fragments (YYYY-MM and YYYY) are also accepted.
[source]	A15	String	2	Code of the nature of the location where the PGRFA was collected. See Table 6 below.
[bwiews]	A16	String	16	FAO WIEWS code of the breeding organization. See "Actor element" for details. Any number of <breeder> can be provided.
[bpid]	A16	String	16	Easy-SMTA PID of the breeding organization, legal entity or individual. See "Actor element" for details.
[bname]	A16	String	128	Surname and name for individuals or organization name of the breeder. See "Actor element" for details.
[baddress]	A16	String	128	Address of the breeding organization, legal entity or individual . Multiple lines are accepted. See "Actor element" for details.
[bcountry]	A16	String	3	ISO-3166 alpha-3 country code (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ISO_3166-1_alpha-3) of the breeding organization, legal entity or individual. See "Actor element" and Table 7 for details.
[ancestry]	A17	String	65.536	Pedigree or other description of the ancestry of the PGRFA and how it was bred.

Response

If the request passes the preliminary checks, GLIS validates the XML object included in the HTTPS POST and responds with an XML object as follows:

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<response>
  <sampleid>[sampleID]</sampleid>
  <genus>[genus]</genus>
  <doi>[DOI]</doi>
  <error>[message]</error>
</response>
```

where:

[sampleid]	is the local sample identifier sent in the request
[genus]	is the genus of the PGRFA
[DOI]	is the DOI associated with the PGRFA upon registration
[message]	is the error message generated during the validation of the registration request

The `<error>` element is present if any problem is found with the registration request and `<doi>` is not present as the registration has failed. Error messages are usually self-explanatory.

Please note that if the registration message includes an already existing DOI for the PGRFA in element `<sampledoic>`, it will be returned in `<doi>`. Also, the `<genus>` element will be present if it was provided in the registration request.

In some institutions local identifiers are assigned separately for each collection. This means that the local identifier, indicated in `<sampleid>`, alone would not be sufficient to uniquely identify the record to which the newly minted DOI should be associated. In those cases, the pair (`genus`, `sampleid`) is unique and this is why the genus is returned in the reply if it was provided in the registration request.

PGRFA registration (for *in situ* material)

While they have a very similar structure, the registration and update messages differ for *ex situ* and *in situ* materials. In this chapter, the registration message for *in situ* material is described, please refer to the corresponding chapter for the *ex situ* material. In this chapter, PGRFA and population are used interchangeably.

The purpose of this transaction is to obtain a DOI associated to the PGRFA by providing a set of descriptors in the registration request. However, if a DOI obtained through a service other than GLIS is already associated to the PGRFA, it must be provided in the request so that GLIS will not assign a new DOI but adopt the one provided.

The registration message contains metadata to be associated to the DOI. Providing as much information as possible is recommended because it will facilitate users when they resolve DOIs in GLIS or discover PGRFA using the metadata provided.

Request

The general structure of the XML registration request is as follows:

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<register>
  <mandatory elements>
  <recommended elements>
</register>
```

There is only one `<register>` element referring to a single PGRFA. It contains mandatory elements and may contain optional elements.

Minimal example

The following is a minimal example with just mandatory and some recommended elements.

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<register username="cgn" password="Passw0rd">
  <manager>
    <pid>00AC55</pid>
```

```

</manager>
<popid>P-123</popid>
<date>1986-05-12</date>
<genus>Hordeum</genus>
<occctry>ANG</occctry>
<targets>
  <target>
    <value>http://www.nordgen.org/sgsv/index.php?unit_id=239741</value>
    <kws>
      <kw>5</kw>
    </kws>
  </target>
</targets>
<biostatus>300</biostatus>
<species>vulgare</species>
<spauth>L.</spauth>
<subtaxa>subsp. vulgare</subtaxa>
<stauth>L.</stauth>
<mlsstatus>1</mlsstatus>
<historical>n</historical>
</register>

```

Actor element

A block of elements is used to identify the manager of the population or where it is conserved *ex situ*.

In these cases, the composition of the elements block is:

```

<wiews>[wiews]</wiews>
<pid>[pid]</pid>
<indherv>[ih]</indherv>
<name>[name]</name>
<address>[address]</address>
<country>[country]</country>
<id>[id]</id>

```

Where:

- [wiews] is the FAO WIEWS Institute code (<http://www.fao.org/wiews>)
- [pid] is the Permanent Identifier assigned by Easy-SMTA (<https://mls.planttreaty.org>)
- [ih] is the Index Herbariorum of the *ex situ* holder. This element is ignored for the managing entity or individual
- [name] is the name of the individual or organization
- [address] is the address of the individual or organization
- [country] is the ISO-3166 alpha-3 country code (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ISO_3166-1_alpha-3). Please note that the extensions listed in Table 7 below do not apply to *in situ* material
- [id] is the sample ID in the *ex situ* holder's collection. This element is ignored for the managing entity or individual

For the managing entity or individual, the <pid> is always available (as registrants must be registered users of Easy-SMTA) and must be provided (if available, the WIEWS code should also be provided). For holders of *ex situ* materials, the preferred way of identifying the *ex situ* material corresponding to the population is providing its GLIS DOI. If the GLIS DOI is not present, providing one among the WIEWS code, the PID or the Index Herbariorum is enough as GLIS can fetch the information from WIEWS, Easy-SMTA or the Index Herbariorum as appropriate. However, only for the *ex situ* holder, when none of the three codes is available, name, address and country should be indicated.

If more than one among <wiews>, <pid>, <indherv> and the explicit elements (<name>, <address> and <country>) are present, the order of precedence is <pid> => <wiews> => <indherv> => explicit elements. If explicit elements are used, at least name and country must be present, address is optional.

XML request object

The body of the HTTPS POST registration request is as follows. Elements marked with * can be repeated multiple times. Some elements can be specified instead of others. See the element description for mandatory requirements and other details. The order of the elements within their parent element is irrelevant. Optional elements may be indicated as empty (e.g. `<element/>` or `<element></element>`) or omitted altogether.

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<register username="[username]" password="[password]">
  <manager>
    <wiews>[mwiews]</wiews>
    <pid>[mpid]</pid>
    <name>[mname]</name>
    <address>[maddress]</address>
    <country>[mcountry]</country>
  </manager>
  <sampledoi>[sampledoi]</sampledoi>
  <popid>[popid]</popid>
  <date>[date]</date>
  <genus>[genus]</genus>
  <species>[species]</species>
  <spauth>[spauth]</spauth>
  <subtaxa>[subtaxa]</subtaxa>
  <stauth>[stauth]</stauth>
  <biostatus>[biostatus]</biostatus>
  <mlsstatus>[mlsstatus]</mlsstatus>
  <occctry>[occctry]</occctry>
  <historical>[hist]</historical>
  <targets>
    <target>*
      <value>[tvalue]</value>
      <kws>
        <kw>[tkw]</kw>*
      </kws>
    </target>
  </targets>
  <site>
    <loc>[location]</loc>
    <lat>[lat]</lat>
    <lon>[lon]</lon>
    <datum>[datum]</datum>
    <elevation>[elevation]</elevation>
    <siteprot>[siteprot]</siteprot>
    <consaction>[consact]</consaction>
  </collection>
  <exsitu>
    <holder>*
      <wiews>[hwiews]</wiews>
      <pid>[hpid]</pid>
      <indherb>[hih]<(indherb>
      <name>[hname]</name>
      <address>[haddress]</address>
      <country>[hcountry]</country>
      <id>[hlocid]</id>
    </holder>
  </exsitu>
</register>
```

where (unless otherwise specified, elements are optional, the DID column refers to the descriptor ID):

Field	DID	Type	Max length or format	Description
[username]	N/A	String	128	Username assigned by the GLIS System Administrator to the requesting system. Mandatory.

[password]	N/A	String	128	Password assigned by the GLIS System Administrator to the requesting system. Mandatory.
[mwiews]	M01	String	16	FAO WIEWS Institute code of the organization managing the PGRFA. See "Actor element" for details.
[mpid]	M01	String	16	Easy-SMTA PID of the organization, legal entity or individual managing the PGRFA. See "Actor element" for details.
[mname]	M01	String	128	Surname and name of individuals or organization name of the organization or legal entity managing the PGRFA. See "Actor element" for details.
[maddress]	M01	String	128	Address of the organization, legal entity or individual managing the PGRFA. See "Actor element" for details.
[mcountry]	M01	String	3	ISO-3166 alpha-3 country code (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ISO_3166-1_alpha-3) of the organization, legal entity or individual managing the PGRFA. See "Actor element" for details.
[sampledoi]	N/A	String	128	A Digital Object Identifier (DOI) obtained from a service other than GLIS and that is already assigned to the PGRFA.
[popid]	M02	String	128	A string that <i>uniquely</i> identifies the PGRFA that is being registered. This value will be returned by GLIS in the response message and is assumed to be used to associate the DOI to the corresponding material in the local database. You must provide <popid> even if <sampledoi> is provided. In case you use the DOI as unique identifier in your local database, you can repeat it in <popid>. Mandatory. Please read more details in the "HTTPS reply" chapter.
[date]	M03	Date	YYYY-MM-DD	Date in which PGRFA was observed. Date fragments (YYYY-MM and YYYY) are also accepted. Mandatory.
[genus]	M04	String	64	The taxon of the genus for the PGRFA. Mandatory.
[species]	M04	String	128	Specific epithet of the PGRFA scientific name. If not provided, sp. is assumed
[occctry]	M05	String	3	ISO-3166 alpha-3 country code (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ISO_3166-1_alpha-3) of the country where the PGRFA is observed.
[tvalue]	R01	String	256	URL of the target page where additional information on the PGRFA can be found. The URL must be URL-encoded. Any number of <target> elements can be provided.
[tkw]	R01	String	16	Code of the keyword indicating the type of information that will be found at the given target URL. See Table 2 below.
[biostatus]	R02	String	3	Biological status of the PGRFA. See Table 3 below.
[spauth]	R03	String	64	Authority for the specific epithet
[subtaxa]	R03	String	128	Any additional infra-specific taxon such as subspecies, variety, form, Group and so on
[stauth]	R03	String	64	Authority for the subtaxon at the most detailed level provided
[mlsstatus]	R04	String	2	Code that identifies the status of the PGRFA with regard to the MLS. See Table 8 below.
[hist]	R05	String	1	Indicates whether the PGRFA no longer exists. Allowed value is y/n with y=population does no longer exist and n=population exists
[loc]	R06	String	128	Description of the location where the PGRFA was observed
[lat]	R06	String	10	Latitude where the PGRFA was observed in ddd.xxxxx (up to 5 decimals, preceded by minus sign for S) format. No spaces are allowed.
[lon]	R06	String	10	Longitude where the PGRFA was observed in ddd.xxxxx (up to 5 decimals, preceded by minus sign for W) format. No spaces are allowed.
[datum]	R06	String	16	Geodetic <i>datum</i> of the lat/lon coordinates
[elevation]	R06	Integer	16	Elevation of occurrence site in metres above sea level
[siteprot]	R06	String	1	Code of the legal protection on the occurrence site. See Table 9 below.

[consact]	R06	String	16	Code of the conservation action(s) in place. See Table 10 below. This element can contain multiple codes separated by " ". For instance, to specify "Species Management" and "Education and Legislation", enter "3 4". Spaces are not allowed.
[hwiews]	R07	String	16	FAO WIEWS Institute code of the organization conserving <i>ex situ</i> samples of the PGRFA. See "Actor element" for details.
[hpid]	R07	String	16	Easy-SMTA PID of the organization, legal entity or individual conserving <i>ex situ</i> samples of the PGRFA. See "Actor element" for details.
[hih]	R07	String	16	Index Herbariorum code of the herbarium conserving <i>ex situ</i> samples of the PGRFA. See "Actor element" for details.
[hname]	R07	String	128	Surname and name of individuals or organization name of the organization or legal entity conserving <i>ex situ</i> samples of the PGRFA. See "Actor element" for details.
[haddress]	R07	String	128	Address of the organization, legal entity or individual conserving <i>ex situ</i> samples of the PGRFA. See "Actor element" for details.
[hcountry]	R07	String	3	ISO-3166 alpha-3 country code (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ISO_3166-1_alpha-3) of the organization, legal entity or individual conserving <i>ex situ</i> samples of the PGRFA. See "Actor element" for details.
[hlocid]	R07	String	128	GLIS DOI or identifier of the sample in the <i>ex situ</i> collection.

Response

If the request passes the preliminary checks, GLIS validates the XML object included in the HTTPS POST and responds with an XML object as follows:

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<response>
  <popid>[popID]</popid>
  <genus>[genus]</genus>
  <doi>[DOI]</doi>
  <error>[message]</error>
</response>
```

where:

[popid] is the population ID sent in the request
 [genus] is the genus of the PGRFA
 [DOI] is the DOI associated with the PGRFA upon registration
 [message] is the error message generated during the validation of the registration request

The <error> element is present if any problem is found with the registration request and <doi> is not present as the registration has failed. Error messages are usually self-explanatory.

Please note that if the registration message includes an already existing DOI for the PGRFA in element <sampledo>, it will be returned in <doi>.

In some institutions local identifiers are assigned separately for each genus. This means that the population identifier, indicated in <popid>, alone would not be sufficient to uniquely identify the record to which the newly minted DOI should be associated. In those cases, the pair (genus, popid) is unique and this is why the genus is returned in the reply.

PGRFA update (for both *ex situ* and *in situ* material)

Updating the descriptors associated with an already registered PGRFA is done using a message similar to the registration one described above. The idea would be that the query and the preparation of the XML message to be sent to GLIS would be quite the same for registrations and updates.

The only differences are:

- the XML root is <update> instead of <register>
- the <sampledo> element is mandatory and must contain the DOI of the PGRFA whose descriptors are being updated. Such DOI must have been previously registered in GLIS

- if the <targets> element is missing or empty, targets and associated keyword codes are left unchanged

All other rules and remarks provided on the registration chapter corresponding to the conservation type (*ex situ* or *in situ*) apply. Using the update request, it is possible to modify any descriptor associated with the material, including targets. Relationships can be edited as appropriate but only limited to those in which the PGRFA is subject of the relationship (i.e. the ancestry or those that were submitted during registration of the same PGRFA). It is not possible to modify relationships to this PGRFA that were established when other PGRFA were registered (i.e. the progeny).

The provided XML document is validated through the same procedure used for the registration request; error messages and the success response are exactly the same.

Please bear in mind that changing the <sampleid> or <popid>, although possible, should be done with care and **never to reuse a DOI assigned to another material or population**. Should you have a material or a population that is no longer existing, please change the corresponding <historical> descriptor. This is critical because the lost material or population may have been cited in publications and/or datasets or be the ancestor of other materials. Reusing the DOI would cause great confusion.

Adding new targets to a DOI

When new information is produced about a PGRFA already associated to a GLIS DOI, it is possible to use this message that implements the addition of a new target to a DOI already registered in GLIS.

The structure of the XML document to put into the HTTPS POST body is as follows

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<addtargets username="[username]" password="[password]">
  <doi>[DOI]</doi>
  <targets>
    <target>*
      <url>[url]</url>
      <kws>
        <kw>[tkw]</kw>*
      </kws>
    </target>
    ...
  </targets>
</addtargets>
```

The <target> and <kw> elements can be repeated any number of times. However, the message refers to a single DOI, so the <doi> element must be present exactly once.

The placeholder's meaning is:

[DOI]	the DOI of the PGRFA to which the targets are being added. Must be present in GLIS. Use the DOI itself (i.e. 10.xxx/yyy), do not use prefixes doi: or https://doi.org/
[url]	the URL of the target web page or resource
[tkw]	the keyword code associated to the target, see Table 2 below. At least one keyword code must be present

Response

If the request passes the preliminary checks, GLIS validates the XML object included in the HTTPS POST and responds with an XML object as follows:

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<response>
  <sampleid>[sampleID]</sampleid>
  <genus>[genus]</genus>
  <doi>[DOI]</doi>
  <error>[message]</error>
</response>
```

where:

[sampleid]	is the local sample identifier sent in the request
[genus]	is the genus of the PGRFA

[DOI] is the DOI associated with the PGRFA upon registration
 [message] is the error message generated during the validation of the registration request

The <error> element is present if any problem is found with the request. If the message is malformed, the other elements may be missing due to the impossibility of properly parsing the request. Error messages are usually self-explanatory.

Coding tables

This section lists the codes used in the elements above unless a link is provided to some external reference site in the element description. Codes must be entered exactly as shown.

Table 1: [method]

Code	Description
acqu	Acquisition
ihcp	In-house copy
ihva	In-house variant
nodl	Novel distinct PGRFA
obna	Observation - Natural
obin	Inherited

Table 2: [tkw]

Code	Description
1	Passport data
1.1	Genealogy
1.2	Collection documents
2	Characterization
3	Evaluation
3.1	Chemical analysis
3.2	Abiotic stress
3.3	Biotic stress
3.4	Biochemical markers
3.5	Molecular markers
3.6	Cytological characters
3.7	Genomics
3.8	Phenomics
4	Environments
5	Multimedia

Table 3: [biostatus, only for *ex situ* material]

Code	Description
100	Wild
110	Natural
120	Semi-natural/wild
130	Semi-natural/sown
200	Weedy
300	Traditional cultivar/landrace
400	Breeding/research material
410	Breeder's line
411	Synthetic population
412	Hybrid
413	Founder stock/base population
414	Inbred line (parent of hybrid cultivar)
415	Segregating population
416	Clonal selection
420	Genetic stock
421	Mutant
422	Cytogenetic stocks
423	Other genetic stocks
500	Advanced or improved cultivar
600	GMO
999	Other

Table 4: [itype]

Code	Description
ark	ARK
genesysuuid	Genesys UUID
gmsid	GMS ID
lsid	LSID
purl	PURL
sgsvid	Global Seed Vault ID
n/a	Other

Table 5: [mlsstatus, only for *ex situ* material]

Code	Description
0	Not available under the MLS
1	Available under the MLS
11	The PGRFA is of a crop listed in Annex I and is under the management and control of a Contracting Party to the Treaty and in the public domain
12	The sample is in an international collection under Article 15 of the Treaty
13	The holder received the PGRFA with an SMTA
14	The holder has voluntarily placed the PGRFA in the MLS
15	The PGRFA is derived from, and distinct from, material previously received from the MLS, is still under development and not yet ready for commercialization, and may be made available at the discretion of the developer, with an SMTA

Table 6: [source]

Code	Description
10	Wild habitat
11	Forest or woodland
12	Shrubland
13	Grassland
14	Desert or tundra
15	Acquatic habitat
20	Farm or cultivated habitat
21	Field
22	Orchard
23	Backyard, kitchen or home garden (urban, peri-urban or rural)
24	Fallow land
25	Pasture
26	Farm store
27	Threshing floor
28	Park
30	Market or shop
40	Institute, Experimental station, Research organization, Genebank
50	Seed company
60	Weedy, disturbed or ruderal habitat
61	Roadside
62	Field margin
99	Other

Table 7: Extensions to the ISO-3166 alpha-3 list of country codes

To address the historical or approximate nature of country information available in some cases, according to the ISO-3166 standard, the following user-defined and historical codes are also available in addition to the standard ones.

Name	Code
Alpine	XAL
Andes	XAN

Arabia	XAR
Australasia	XAA
Australia & New Zealand	XAZ
Benelux	XBE
Bengal	XBN
Cape Horn	XCH
Caribbean	XCR
Caspian	XCP
Central Africa	XCF
Central America	XCA
Czechoslovakia	CSK
East Africa	XEF
Eastern Europe	XEE
Far East	XFE
German Democratic Rep.	DDR
Germany, Federal Rep. of	BRD
Himalaya	XHM
Iberia	XIB
Mediterranean	XMD
Middle East	XME
New Hebrides	NHB
North Africa	XNF
North America	XNA
North-East Asia	XNE
Pacific Ocean	XPO
Panama Canal Zone	PCZ
Sahara	XSH
Scandinavia	XSC
Sea of Japan	XSJ
Serbia and Montenegro	SCG
South America	XSA
South East Asia	XAS
Southern Africa	XSF
Southern Europe	XSE
Union of Soviet Soc. Rep.	SUN
Upper Volta	HVO
West Africa	XWF
Western Europe	XWE
Yemen, Democratic	YMD
Yugoslavia	YUG

Additionally, to designate International Institutions such as the CGIAR as provenance of the PGRFA being registered, the following codes can also be used

Name	Code
Africa Rice	XAB
Bioversity International	XAC
CIAT	XAD
CIMMYT	XAE

CIP	XAF
ICARDA	XAG
ICRAF	XAH
ICRISAT	XAI
IITA	XAJ
ILRI	XAK
IRRI	XAM

Table 8: [mlsstatus, only for *in situ* material]

Code	Description
0	Not available under the MLS
1	Available under the MLS

Table 9: [siteprot, only for *in situ* material]

Code	Description
0	Not protected by legislation
1	Strict nature reserve
2	Wilderness area
3	National park
4	Natural monument or feature
5	Habitat/species management area
6	Protected landscape or seascape
7	Protected area with sustainable use of natural resources
8	Other effective conservation measures (OECM)

Table 10: [consact, only for *in situ* material]

Code	Description
0	No conservation actions
1	Monitoring and Planning
2	Land/Water Protection and Management
3	Species Management
4	Education and Legislation
99	Other